

THE REPRESENTATION OF MIGRATION IN CONTEMPORARY WORLD LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Migration has emerged as a significant issue in contemporary world literature, representing global dislocation, identity struggles, and cultural hybridity. This study investigates how modern literary works portray migrant experiences, with a focus on identity development, border crossings, and cultural disputes. This article seeks to explain how literature may be used to comprehend the difficulties of migration by examining chosen novels and poems.

INTRODUCTION

Migration has become a defining feature of the modern world, influencing nations, economy, and human lives on a worldwide scale. As individuals transcend boundaries in quest of better opportunities, safety, or freedom, their experiences with displacement, adaptation, and identity creation have emerged as key topics in contemporary international literature. Migration narratives are no longer limited to physical mobility; they also address emotional, cultural, and psychological shifts, providing readers with a deeper knowledge of what it means to leave one's birthplace and traverse new surroundings.

Literature is a strong vehicle for representing migrants' complex experiences, shedding light on both their challenges and perseverance. Novels, poetry, and other literary forms shed light on the realities of migration, exploring issues like belonging, alienation, and cultural hybridity. Scholars such as Homi Bhabha (1994) have stressed the concept of a "third space," in which migrants negotiate between their original and host cultures, resulting in hybrid identities. Similarly, Edward Said (1993) emphasizes how stories of exile and displacement alter notions of home and identity.

This article explores how migration is portrayed in modern global literature, emphasizing important concepts such as cultural hybridity, border crossings, and identity development. By examining a few literary works, this research seeks to show how literature depicts the intricacies of migration, providing readers with a sympathetic perspective on the migrant experience while questioning popular perceptions of displacement.

Methods: 1. Text Selection

Five modern literary works that address migration are examined in this study:

Americanah by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie

Mohsin Hamid's Path to the West

On Earth, Ocean Vuong's We're Momentarily Beautiful
My mother is being taught how to give birth by Warsan Shire.
The Namesake, written by Jhumpa Lahiri

2. Framework for Analysis

The following dimensions are the focus of the study's theme analysis:

Identity Formation: The process via which characters negotiate their identities while being uprooted.

The representation of physical, cultural, and emotional boundaries is known as "border crossings." **Cultural Hybridity:** Intersections of diverse cultural influences and the ensuing hybrid identities.

3. Information Gathering

The selection of passages was based on how well they captured the realities of migration, including cultural alienation, nostalgia, and adaptation. Psychoanalytic and postcolonial perspectives were used to evaluate these passages.

RESULTS:

Identity Development

Americanah depicts the protagonist's struggle with race and identity in the United States, emphasizing the impact of outside judgments on self-identity. Americanah depicts the protagonist's struggle with race and identity in the United States, emphasizing the impact of external perceptions on one's own identity.

Lahiri's The Namesake depicts generational identity conflicts among Indian immigrants in the United States, highlighting the contradiction between cultural tradition and assimilation.

2. Border-crossings

Exit West depicts border crossings using magical realism, emphasizing the emotional cost of exile and the human desire for freedom.

Warsan Shire's poetry clearly depicts the agony of fleeing one's homeland and the difficulties of obtaining asylum.

3. Cultural Hybridity

Americanah depicts the protagonist's struggle with race and identity in the United States, emphasizing the impact of outside judgments on self-identity. The blend of cultures. The protagonist in On Earth We're Briefly Gorgeous experiences both strength and alienation as a result of their cultural hybridity in this multi-layered story.

DISCUSSION: The results show that modern global literature presents migration as a difficult yet transformational experience, providing a multifaceted picture of the phenomenon. By means of literary tropes such as metaphor, symbolism, and narrative structure, these works shed light on the intricacies of identity and displacement.

Intersection with Postcolonial Theory: Bhabha's (1994) idea of the "third space," where new identities arise, is reflected in a number of writings.

Emotional and Psychological Impact: By illustrating the emotional upheaval and resiliency of migrants, literature gives readers a sympathetic perspective on migration.

CONCLUSION

World literature of today reflects the topic of migration by presenting the many experiences of those who have been displaced. Through the examination of identity, borders, and cultural hybridity, these literary works advance our knowledge of how migration affects both people and societies. Future studies could go farther by examining less-studied areas and how migration is portrayed in literature.

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